

Multiresolutional Intelligent Controller for Baby Robot

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an algorithm of unsupervised learning for applications in robotics. Minimum initial knowledge is presumed (“bootstrap knowledge”). The learning system uses the newly arrived information to extract rules of motion and construct the World Representation. The concept of recursive generalization is explored as the main tool of rule extraction and knowledge organization. The experiment in learning is described based upon simulation of a 2D and a 3D mobile system.

I. INTRODUCTION: THE BABY ROBOT CONCEPT

The architecture of the Intelligent Controller is accepted following the results from [1, 2]: i.e. it is based on a multiresolutional system of nested loops (“perception - World Representation - Decision Making - Actuation - World - Sensors”). This system has not been equipped with learning; our paper tries to close the gap which is usually avoided by declaring all necessary knowledge available and all sensor information interpretable. The later properties do not hold in any real system, thus, a learning system is vitally important to make the control system fully intelligent.

The concept of Baby Robot was first introduced in [3, 4] and further developed in [5, 6]. The autonomous robot is presented as a “baby” – that is, a system with no a priori knowledge of the world in which it operates, but with behavior acquisition techniques that allow it to build this knowledge from the experiences of actions within a particular environment. The challenge is to determine whether the World Representation can be constructed without any external human-interpreter, based only upon its own experience of functioning. The learning techniques are rooted in a recursive algorithm for inductive generalization of nested schemata molded from processes of early cognitive development in humans. The algorithm extracts data from the environment, and after using clustering and abduction, it creates schemata inter-

preted as control rules. This system is robust enough to deal with a constantly changing environment; such changes provoke the creation of new schemata by further generalizing from experiences. The algorithm is capable of automatically generating the hierarchy of task decomposition, a job that is performed in existing systems only by organizing the knowledge of a human-expert.

The system searches in a multiresolutional knowledge base which is a self-generating structure; thus, the complexity is pseudo-polynomial which ensures learnability [7]. Although the traditional approach to autonomous navigation involves off-line path planning with a known world map, in most of the real tasks the environment is not well known. The conditions of the assignment are ever-changing, for example: absence of gravity in the case of space; and sophisticated, hard to predict obstacles; like nonlinear hydrodynamics in the underwater case. Baby Robot gathers data from its sensors and then uses a schema-discovery system to extract concepts, form schemata and create a quantitative/conceptual semantic network.

Experimenting with Baby-Robot is important in unknown media because the rules of required behavior do not coincide with human intuitions. This concept reflects our expectation that the simulated device can acquire previously unknown schemata from the results of its own experience. When the Baby Robot is first dropped onto a terrain, into space, or under water, it does not have any experiences and its sensors and actuators do not have any special meaning for Baby Robot: it will learn their meaning from its own experience. At first randomly, then in a directed manner (when new schemata are created) Baby Robot collects experiences that allow it to learn schemata to represent the function of its actuators and sensors. Then a decision making algorithm activates these schemata to achieve the goal given by its creator, or the sub-goals that it finds.

In our initial simulation experiment the goal of functioning is to minimize the distance to a beacon. The results of simulation are positive. The Baby

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Figure 1: Architecture of intelligent systems

Robot displays the ability to learn a number of maneuvers and to build a multiresolutional knowledge base ready for subsequent use.

II. STRUCTURE OF THE INTELLIGENT CONTROLLER

II.A. The Core of Intelligent Information Processing

The core of intelligence information processing can be divided in two packages (Figure 1):

1. Generalization algorithms build up the system of knowledge representation. These algorithms are in charge of the organization and interpretation of incoming information developing the World Model and creation of the rules of operation. The rules are generalized from experiences. The generalization algorithm works both bottom-up in the sense that rules are generalized from experiences. A higher resolution entity (the experiences) is transformed into a lower resolution one (rules). This algorithm consists of three supportive sub-routines.
 - (a) Focusing attention is the first step in the creation of the rules. This procedure separates the unwanted experiences from the ones that are suited for the creation of the rules.
 - (b) The creation of the classes is the second step in the creation of rules.
 - (c) Abduction [8] is the third and last step of generalization where the classes are compared and/or properly arranged.
2. Decision Making algorithms determine which action should be produced in order to achieve the goal.
 - (a) Focusing Attention allows for selecting the rule that should be applied to a concrete situation.
 - (b) Combinatorial search uses synthesis of different possibility strings of rules that could be applied from this situation to achieve the goal.

II.B. Decision Making Algorithms

In this paper, we will demonstrate how the rules in the knowledge base are created by clustering experimental data. For now let's assume (in order to understand the decision making algorithm) that these rules have already been created with the following characteristics:

1. Rules in the database (hypotheses or schemata) fall in one of the following categories:

Leaf: If situation (SI) and goal (GO) applying action (AC) will yield goodness (GD). Where SI is a set of sensor intervals, GO is the goal situation, AC is a vector in the actuator space, and GD is a measure of expected performance.

Branch: If not SI and GO then go to SI with maximum GD .

These two types of rules imply their further organization in a hierarchy.

2. The following laws are used to form the hierarchy of rules:

- (a) Given a rule RU_n its sons (lower level in the hierarchy) are composed of leaves and/or branches with GO equal to SI of RU_n .
- (b) The lowest resolution level of the hierarchy has only one rule RU_0 which has the form: "If $\emptyset$ then go to SI_0 ", in other words "Always go to SI_0 " where SI_0 is the goal assigned by the creator of the system.
- (c) Only branches can have sons.
- (d) Every branch RU_{br} has a brother (same father and same level) with the opposite SI and a recommendation about what to do in SI .

The purpose of the decision making algorithm is to find the correct consecutively assigned set of actions that will bring the system to achieve the goal assigned by the source of goals. The greedy algorithm is the simplest way to search through the database. The method can be explained as follows:

1. Assign the lowest rule (RU_0) as the starting rule RU_{aux} .
2. Pick the son that has a SI that includes the current situation and has the highest goodness of the system and assign it to RU_{aux} . Branches have goodness 0.
3. If RU_{aux} is a leaf, exit and apply the action recommended by RU_{aux} else assign the branch to RU_{aux} and go to 2.

This algorithm is simple and quick which is important because it has to be applied at each time step. We have implemented other search algorithms

Figure 2: The Generalization Algorithm

like A* but at this stage of development they do not give greater advantages over the greedy search and they are significantly slower. We also tested a non-consecutive procedure using multidimensional clustering and we found it less efficient and not consistent with the concept of early learning development. The examples given in Section 6 were implemented using greedy search.

II.C. Generalization Algorithms

The generalization algorithm is composed of the following steps (Figure 2):

1. The whole database of experiences is separated in two classes: admissible and non-admissible. Admissible experiences are “good” experiences.
2. The representation of each experience is enhanced. Enhancing means that new labels are included in the experiences, these labels are combinations among sensors values, among actuators values, and between sensors and actuator values.
3. Using the enhanced experience, it creates classes of enhanced experiences.
4. Each of these classes of enhanced experiences becomes a hypothesis.
5. The hypotheses are stored in the database of hypotheses.

It is possible to say that the algorithm of generalization creates the new concept (rule) by making clusters of experience using a measure closeness among them: first roughly and then finer and finer. As we have seen in the first step it creates clusters by goodness (which can also be considered a measure of closeness) and then it creates classes of similarities among situations and actions. This algorithm can be applied in a nested manner in order to create a goal decom-

position tree or knowledge base. The algorithm of generalization takes as input a goal and the database of experiences; and it processes these experiences until it comes out with a set of Hypotheses.

The Hypotheses are then in the database of Hypotheses as a tree where each hypothesis is related to its father by the goal. Since the son hypothesis has a new goal (the father’s situation) it has a new measure of goodness.

The goodness used to discriminate the experiences that created the son hypothesis were chosen using the definition of goodness, which is how much closer did it get to the goal, which in this case is the father’s situation. In other words, since it is not possible to find rules from all the situations since only good experiences are selected to the classification procedure, the other parts of the space will have as goal the situations where we have a “direct” rule of action to the original goal.

A second measure that we use later on to decide which rule should be applied is a belief measure. This belief measure is calculated using the “density” of the cluster that formed the rule. By this, we mean that the belief increases the more experiences we have in the cluster. This belief measure is used by the decision making in a joint goodness-belief measure that allow to pick the most trustworthy rule for the current situation and goal.

When the database of Hypotheses grows, it becomes a tree of task decomposition. The experience storage has allocated a maximum amount of space. When the number of experiences reaches this maximum, and a new experience is collected, then this experience will be stored in the place occupied by the oldest experience in the database. This procedure will create a “wrap-around” or “wheel” of experiences where we store only the later ones.

III. SIMULATION OF THE INTELLIGENT CONTROLLER WITH UNSUPERVISED LEARNING

III.A. Structure of the Platform and Goal

A simulation for a mobile platform was implemented to test the generalization algorithm. The sensors return the distance to target (D), the heading (H), and the angle to target (A). The actuators are simply go forward (G), and rotate (R). The assigned goal is “make $D=0$ ”.

In other words, the goal that we assign will cause the learning algorithm to create a control structure that will allow the mobile platform to achieve the target. Following the algorithm delineated in the previous chapter, the decision making algorithm searches in the database of hypotheses and it finds the only existing rule shown in the previous figure. It realizes that it does not know how to “make $D=0$ ” so it

1. Goodness	10. D-R	19. D+G
2. Distance (D)	11. H-A	20. D+R
3. Heading (H)	12. H-G	21. H+A
4. Angle to Target (A)	13. H-R	22. H+G
5. Go forward (G)	14. A-G	23. H+R
6. Rotate(R)	15. A-R	24. A+G
7. D-H	16. G-R	25. A+R
8. D-A	17. D+H	26. G+R
9. D-G	18. D+A	

Table 1: Enhanced Representation Sensors and Actuators in Baby Robot

applies a random sequence to the actuators collecting experiences. The next step is the generalization algorithm. The first step is to separate the “good” experiences from the bad. In this case the goal is “make $D=0$ ” the goodness of an experience is defined as “Delta D”. The next step is to enhance the representation of these “good” experiences. The enhanced representation is ordered as shown in Table 1. This notation will be used for all figures.

III.B. Step by Step Recursive Generalization

The first step that the algorithm of generalization does is to check the database of Hypotheses. The only schema present in the database says that it should “Make $D=0$ ”. Since there is nothing in the database about what to do in order to “Make $D=0$ ” it assigns “ $D=0$ ” as the goal, and collects a random sequence of experiences. The next step in the algorithm of generalization is the creation of the classes of experiences. The clustering algorithm discovers two classes given the following rules of unification of classes:

- If there are two consequent classes that have arbitrarily close maximums and the minimum separating them is arbitrarily close to the maximums, then the two classes are unified.
- If a class occupies the complete range in that coordinate, (i.e. there is only one class that includes all experiences in that coordinate) then the coordinate is discarded as rule candidate.

They correspond to the actuator “go forward” and the enhanced representation sensor “Heading - Angle to Target”. These two Hypotheses have an important difference. The first one gives a recommendation about what actuator to use in this situation. In the second one, the hypothesis says that if we are not in this situation we should go to this situation.

The problem with the second hypothesis is that there is nothing in the database of Hypotheses that gives instructions about how to “Make $(H-A=0.1)$ ”. Thus, the generalization algorithm starts again:

Figure 3: The database of Hypotheses at this step

1. a new goodness measure is taken by checking whether the experience brought it closer or further to the new goal;
2. the new goal is to “make $H-A=0.1$ ”;
3. all the experiences are re-ranked using the new goodness measure for the new goal;
4. the “best” experiences are selected using one of the previously selected methods;
5. these experiences are sent again to the classification algorithm, in other words, new eventgrams are created for the new goal and the classification algorithm creates new clusters which will be used for creating rules to follow the new goal.

In Figure 4, we show the eventgrams for the same experiences and the new goal (“make $H-A=0.1$ ”).

These 300 experiences are sent to the averaging algorithm which finds two clusters in coordinate 6 which corresponds to the actuator “Rotate”. These two clusters become two Hypotheses that get incorporated in the database as shown in Figure 5. In this figure “Rotate 0.9” and “Rotate 9.8” correspond to rotate right and rotate left. The “S2” is extracted from the experiences in which the rotate right command was applied and “S3” from the rotate left experiences.

III.C. Baby Robot for 2D Operation

The robot for 2D Operation is called the Land Baby Robot (LBR). The simulation is shown in Figure 6, on the left we can see the mobile platform and on the right it is possible to see the target.

Figure 7 shows a random path taken initially by LBR in order to collect experiences to create hypotheses and eventually schemata.

Figure 8 shows the behavior of LBR after the first set of Hypotheses are collected.

Figure 9 shows the numerical improvement upon the original hypothesis that yields better paths.

Figure 10 shows a quasi-optimal path that LBR converges to.

III.D. Baby Robot for 3D Operation

The platform for 3D operation is called underwater Baby Robot (UBR). The sensors given to the UBR are:

1. Distance to the target.
2. The three Euler angles to the target.

Figure 4: The eventgram of 3000 experiences (left); the eventgram of the 300 best experiences shown on the right. Note: 22 though 26 were deleted to save space

Figure 5: Database of hypotheses

Figure 6: The Simulation Environment

Figure 7: The initial random motion

Figure 8: The first hypothesis

And the actuators given to UBR are:

1. Propulsion.
2. Angles of the two rudders.

Figure 11 shows an example of a learned hypothesis. At the beginning, there are some random movements. Then, a hypothesis is generalized, showing a spiral movement of an incorrect hypothesis of spiraling. After more experiences are collected it will realize the performance could be improved and a new hypothesis will be generalized and this one may be thrown away.

Figure 12 shows the first trial to go to the goal. The traces were left on to show how complicated and superfluous is the path. At the beginning of this trial the learning algorithm does not have any knowledge about the environment. It is possible to see four or five different hypotheses that create different motion.

Figure 13 shows some random movements and then the bang-bang control. Note, that we did not teach our robot the concept of “bang-bang” control; it discovered it as a result of the learning process.

After the first set of random movements we can see a sharp change in behavior (Figure 11). The first set of baby schemata is learned and we can see (Figure 13) that the submarine starts applying bang-bang

Figure 9: Numerical improvement

Figure 10: Quasi-optimum path

Figure 11: Random movement and wrong hypothesis of spiraling

control. More details about Baby-Sub and Astro-Baby can be found in [5].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

1. An algorithm that will serve as a subsystem for unsupervised learning is proposed for the Intelligent Controller Structure.
2. This system employs the method of nested clustering.
3. The system simulates and executes the process of decision making.

Figure 12: First trial

Figure 13: Bang-Bang control

4. The system organizes input information into a multiresolutional structure of world representation.
5. Simulation experiments confirm the theoretical premises.

V. REFERENCES

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